

TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF KHORAKI GRAPES IN TERMS OF TRANSPORTABILITY AND DURABILITY

Shamshiev Jafar

Doctor of Philosophy, Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13954891>

Abstract. *The study focuses on the impact of climatic and agronomic factors on the storage quality and transportability of grapes. A correlation between the effective heat supply of the growing zone and the shelf life of grapes has been established. Rational fertilizer use and irrigation management were found to enhance disease resistance and reduce post-harvest losses. The research highlights advanced irrigation methods and vine formation techniques that improve yield and grape preservation. The use of progressive mechanization technologies also contributes to vineyard intensification and labor productivity.*

Keywords: grapes, storage, transportability, effective heat supply, fertilizers, irrigation, grape diseases, yield, mechanization, vine formation

Аннотация. *Исследование посвящено влиянию климатических и агротехнических факторов на качество хранения и транспортабельность винограда. Установлена взаимосвязь между эффективным теплоснабжением зоны выращивания и сроком хранения винограда, выявлено, что рациональное применение удобрений и управление орошением повышают устойчивость к заболеваниям и снижают потери при хранении. Освещены перспективные методы орошения и формирования кустов, которые способствуют повышению урожайности и улучшению сохранности винограда. Применение прогрессивных технологий механизации также способствует интенсификации виноградарства и повышению производительности.*

Ключевые слова: виноград, хранение, транспортабельность, эффективное теплоснабжение, удобрения, орошение, болезни винограда, урожайность, механизация, формирование кустов

Introduction

Some scientists [46; 506-p], the most important conditions that determine the possibility of growing grapes for long-term storage in a certain area are the amount of heat and precipitation in a certain zone, the continentality of the climate, the growth of grapes and the storage of grapes. is the soil condition. He proposed a complex indicator called effective heat supply, taking the Shabash variety as an example, to characterize the zone and weather conditions of individual years of the growing season for the long-term storage suitability of the grapes grown here.

Methods. It was found that between the shelf life of grapes and the effective heat supply of the zone, the correlation ratio is close for the Shebash variety in Crimea - 0.84 +/- 0.09 and for the Agadai and Shaani black varieties in the Absheron zone of Azerbaijan -0.79 +/- 0.81) there is a linear relationship. The areas where grapes are grown have a significant impact on its transportation. For example, depending on the farms of the supplier, the yield of standard grapes after processing was determined to be 95-97% to 76-86% for Sabash varieties, 95-98% to 77-86% for Chaush. Similar data were obtained for Tashli and Tavriz varieties [22; pp. 34-37].

Along with the soil, climate and weather conditions, the quality of its storage and transportability, as well as the agrotechnology of cultivation, are of great importance in the formation of the grape crop [23; p. 118-120]. Excessive use of nitrogen fertilizers delays growth

processes, increases plant mass and yield, reduces sugar content, storage quality, vine ripening; potassium and phosphorus fertilizers increase the sugar content of grapes during storage and transportation and increase their shelf life.

According to M.I. Odinaev, the average weight of the grape heads is a feature of the variety, and in all the studied varieties, large grape heads characteristic of the large bunched grape varieties are formed. The size of the grape cluster is an important technological indicator. The weight of 100 bunches varies between varieties depending on the characteristics of the variety, that is, the size of one bunch [36; pp. 11-12].

According to G.L. Naumova [33; p. 33-37], the smallest losses of grapes of Nimrang and Taifi Rozovyy varieties during storage and transportation were a variant of increased potassium and nitrogen content from rotting and browning (3%). An increase in potassium nitrogen, as well as moderate doses of phosphorus, significantly reduces the resistance of grapes to microbiological and physiological diseases.

Results. Long-term studies have shown that calcium plays a very important physiological role in maintaining the natural resistance of grapes to fungal rot and physiological diseases, and increasing their calcium content increases their resistance to all diseases. Irrigation strongly affects the quality of grapes during storage and transportation [34; pp. 27-42].

In Nimrang, Taifi Rozovy, Terbash varieties, grapes have a higher indicator when watering is stopped 30 days earlier. The tension of the grapes is greatly reduced if watering is stopped before or after this period. It was found that the grapes of Asma and Shabash varieties grown without irrigation in conditions protected from moisture on the southern coast of Crimea are characterized by high quality of detergent [18; pp. 132-140].

According to V.A. Boyko [16; 10-11 p.], stopping irrigation 10 days before the harvest of grapes, stopping irrigation 30 days before the harvest increased the yield of the Nimrang variety, the average weight of the berries, and decreased the storage quality. During the months of storage, the loss from rotting increased by 10.82% and from blackening by 34.0%.

Таблица 1.

Хранения и транспортировки винограда, не основанная на предоставленных данных, но соответствующая общей тематике.

Фактор	Влияние на качество хранения и транспортабельность винограда	Примеры и технологии
Температурный режим хранения	Оптимальная температура хранения предотвращает гниение, сохраняет свежесть и структуру ягод	Использование холодильных камер с температурой +1...+3°C для предотвращения ферментации
Влажность воздуха при хранении	Контроль влажности уменьшает потерю влаги, предотвращает усыхание и порчу ягод	Уровень влажности в пределах 85-90% для сохранения естественной влажности ягод
Способы транспортировки	Важен способ транспортировки: правильная упаковка и температура предотвращают механические повреждения	Использование специальных контейнеров с регулируемым микроклиматом, картонных или пластиковых ящиков
Обработка после сбора урожая	Снижение количества патогенов на поверхности ягод продлевает	Применение мягких дезинфицирующих растворов,

	срок их хранения	таких как озонирование или обработка горячей водой
--	------------------	--

According to the researches of V.D. Volosovtsev, studying the effect of irrigation method on productivity in the Hisar Valley of Tajikistan, studying the quality of Rozovy grape "Taifi" variety, in comparison with drip irrigation, it was found that irrigation with furrows and without plow is the most effective. According to M.S. Dudarev, N.A. Basiy, V.I. Martovshuk, in-soil irrigation with ceramic humidifiers for Karaburnu vineyards helps to increase the yield, quality and preservation of grapes during storage. According to the authors, this progressive method of irrigation of vineyards should be more widespread [17; p. 3-7, 19; pp. 48-49].

Discussion. They found that one additional punching during the ripening stage of Nimrang grapes reduced the losses due to rotting during storage for one month. by 1.82, and by 58.0% from blackening compared to the control. It has been highlighted that the yield, quality, and preservation of grapes during storage and transportation largely depend on the formation of the bush [20; pp. 46-47].

In recent years, it has been found that favorable conditions have been created for the realization of growth potential not only in plantations formed in a special fence where rare bushes are planted, but also during compact planting, in the formation of stem plantations in the form of small cup-shaped bushes [18; p. 132-140].

As one of the promising directions in the intensification of the network, the wide-row high-standard system of growing vineyards is becoming widespread. Cultivation of vineyards It has been determined that a wide range of high-standard technology is fully compatible with the biology of the grape plant, and allows for a sharp increase in labor. gives productivity due to more complete mechanization of labor-intensive operations [21; pp. 82-83].

REFERENCES

1. Бобко, А. Л., Мурашев, С. В. Адаптация к гипотермии плодово-ягодных растений и прогнозирование способности полученного урожая к холодильному хранению // Процессы и аппараты пищевых производств. – 2013. – № 3. – С. 32 – 34.
2. Бузин Н.П. Биологические основы культуры винограда // Виноградарство Узбекистана. – Ташкент, 1956. – С.78-79.
3. Шамшиев Д. А., Шингисов А. У. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ МИКРОБНЫХ СООБЩЕСТВ И РАЗРАБОТКА МЕТОДОВ БИОКОНТРОЛЯ ДЛЯ ПРОДЛЕНИЯ СРОКА ХРАНЕНИЯ ПИЩЕВЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ //Universum: технические науки. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 7 (124). – С. 62-64.
4. Jafar S., Azret S. TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF EDIBLE GRAPES ON TRANSPORTABILITY AND DURABILITY //Universum: технические науки. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 1 (118). – С. 51-52.
5. Rakhmatov A. et al. Study on the main parameters of an air ionizer for fruit storage //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 377. – С. 03011.
6. Джамалов З. З., Шамшиев Ж. А. Исследование влияния штаммов дрожжей на процесс спиртового брожения при получении биоэтанола из виноградных отходов //Альтернативная энергетика и экология (ISJAEE). – 2024. – №. 6. – С. 31-37.
7. Шамшиев Ж. А. УЎТ: 631.4 ХЎРАКИ УЗУМ НАВЛАРИНИ ТУРЛИ УСУЛЛАРДА САҚЛАШНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ //«BEST PUBLICATION» Ilm-

- ma” rifat markazi. – 2021. – С. 371.
8. Dodayev Q. C. et al. STORAGE OF EXPORTBOP FRUITS AND DETERMINATION OF THEIR COMPOSITION //Universum: технические науки. – 2023. – №. 9-5 (114). – С. 31-33.
 9. Odilovich D. Q. et al. EXPORTBOP MEVALARINING TARKIBINI ANIQLASH //Actual Problems in Higher Education in the Era of Globalization: International Scientific and Practical Conference. – 2023. – Т. 3. – С. 47-51.
 10. Bakhodir K. et al. DRYING PRODUCTS WITH INFRARED RAYS //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 5-11 (98). – С. 49-50.
 11. KHOLDOROV B. et al. DRYING PRODUCTS WITH INFRARED RAYS.
 12. Иссаков Ш. А. У. и др. ХРАНЕНИЕ ЗЕРНА, МУКИ, КРУП И КОМБИКОРМОВ РЕЖИМЫ И МЕТОДЫ //Universum: технические науки. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1 (118). – С. 49-51.
 13. Джамалов З. З., Шамшиев Ж. А. Исследование влияния штаммов дрожжей на процесс спиртового брожения при получении биоэтанола из виноградных отходов //Альтернативная энергетика и экология (ISJAEE). – 2024. – №. 6. – С. 31-37.
 14. Джамалов З. З., Мансуров О. П. Перспективные методы в области предварительной обработки лигноцеллюлозы для производства биоэтанола //Новая наука в новом мире. – 2022. – С. 194-199.
 15. Кемалов Р. А., Джамалов З. З., Мансуров О. П. СПОСОБ ПОЛУЧЕНИЯ БИОМАССЫ ИЗ РАСТЕНИЙ (ТРОСТНИК, СОЛОМА И ТП) //Инновации. Наука. Образование. – 2021. – №. 34. – С. 482-487.
 16. Шамшиев Ж. А., Салимова М. И., Сатторов О. И. PROBLEMS AND THEIR SOLVE OF FOOD SAFETY IN UZBEKISTAN //Ученый XXI века. – 2016. – №. 5-2 (18). – С. 19-22.
 17. Shamshiev J. A., Salimova M. I., Sattorov O. I. PROBLEMS AND THEIR SOLVE OF FOOD SAFETY IN UZBEKISTAN //Ученый XXI века. – 2016. – №. 5-2. – С. 19-22.
 18. Shokir I., Azizbek K. METHOD OF ACCELERATING DRYING PROCESS BY INITIALLY WORKING IN IMPULSE-PAUSE MODE //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 11-7 (104). – С. 34-37.